

deprotonated phenolic oxygen is coordinated to the rare earth ion first (in preference to carbonyl oxygen) due to the strong ionic interaction towards the positively charged metal which is followed by the stable five-membered chelate formation with the nitrogen. The IR spectra of the complexes also show a strong unsplit band around 1080 cm^{-1} and a medium unsplit band around 620 cm^{-1} , assignable to the ν_3 and ν_4 vibrations, respectively, of ionic perchlorate. Therefore, the perchlorate is not coordinated¹⁰ as confirmed by conductance studies. Hence a coordination number of six may be assigned to the rare earth ion in these complexes.

The magnetic moment of these complexes (Table 1) show little variation from Van Vleck values suggesting that the $4f$ -electrons, well shielded by the $5s^2 5p^6$ octet, play only a small role in bonding¹¹.

The electronic spectra indicate that all the absorptions due to the $f-f$ transition of the rare earth ions in the visible region are obscured in the present complexes by the strong absorption of the ligand and by the very broad charge transfer band spreading over the whole visible region. Hence the electronic spectra are not very helpful in the investigations of transitions involving the f -electrons of the rare earth ion¹.

The present complexes are of industrial as well as physiological applications. It is interesting to note that the rare earth perchlorate complexes of H-RAP are soluble in common polar solvents whereas the corresponding nitrate complexes are insoluble. Thus the anion change will effect the dye application of these complexes on fibres. Also, these complexes can be recommended to study the change in the physiological action of H-RAP on complexation with the rare earth ions.

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Stability Constants of Mixed Ligand Chelates of Lanthanum(III), Praseodymium(III) and Neodymium(III) with NTA, HEDTA, CYDTA and DTPA as Primary Ligands and some Polymethylene Dicarboxylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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LANTHANUM(III), praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), *N*-hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA), cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (CYDTA) and diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) as primary ligands and polymethylenedicarboxylic acids pimelic acid (PMA), suberic acid (SUA), azelic acid (AZA) and sebacic acid (SEA) as secondary ligands have been investigated at 25, 35 and 45° at fixed ionic strength 0.2 mol dm^{-3} (KNO_3) by potentiometric method and the effects of these mixed ligand chelates on the germination, survival and seedling height of barley plants (*Jav* or *Hordeum vulgare*) was also studied.

Experimental

Solutions of metal nitrates $\text{Ln}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) were prepared in nitric acid. The metal contents were estimated by spectrophotometric^{2,3} and gravimetric⁴ methods. Solutions of primary ligands NTA, Na_2CYDTA , DTPA (B.D.H.), HEDTA (Sigma) and secondary ligands PMA, SUA, AZA, SEA were prepared in oxygen-free double-distilled water.

The experimental details for potentiometric measurement and computational methods were the same as described earlier⁵. The results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The values of first and second dissociation constants are found to be very close in case of all four polymethylenedicarboxylic acids and indicate that these dicarboxylic acids are moderately acidic in nature. The nature of complex formation equilibria whether stepwise or simultaneous was investigated according to the method suggested by Carry and Martell⁶. The primary ligands NTA, HEDTA, CYDTA and DTPA are considered to occupy four, six and eight coordination positions around lanthanide ions. The secondary ligands PMA, SUA, AZA and SEA are penta-, hexa-, hepta- and octamethylenedicarboxylic acids respectively and act as bifunctional oxygen donors and bidentate in mixed ligand chelate formations. The trends in stabilities of mixed ligand chelates with respect to

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SECONDARY LIGANDS AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES

Constant		Ligand			
		PMA	SUA	AZA	SEA
$\log K_1^H$		4.36	4.74	5.08	5.23
$\log K_2^H$		2.49	3.86	4.10	3.83

$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	Metal ion	Secondary ligand	Primary ligand			
			NTA	HEDTA	CYDTA	DTPA
	La ^{III}	PMA	5.44	5.38	5.24	5.09
		SUA	3.33	3.26	3.22	3.20
		AZA	3.75	3.60	3.44	3.52
		SEA	5.94	5.83	5.64	5.34
	Pr ^{III}	PMA	5.34	5.29	5.24	5.14
		SUA	3.38	3.32	3.26	3.22
		AZA	4.80	3.65	3.60	3.55
		SEA	6.18	6.08	5.88	5.44
	Nd ^{III}	PMA	6.24	6.14	5.78	5.88
		SUA	3.42	3.35	3.30	3.27
		AZA	3.92	3.40	3.27	3.22
		SEA	6.24	6.13	6.78	5.78

metal ion M(III) appear to be La^{III} > Pr^{III} > Nd^{III}, and with the change in primary ligand the order is NTA > HEDTA > CYDTA > DTPA.

The biocidal characteristics of these mixed ligand chelates formed in solution were tested in aqueous medium at room temperature. The best effects on germination survival and seedling were observed in case of La^{III} as the metal ion and DTPA as the primary ligand.

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Equilibrium Study on Complex Formation of Samarium(III) and Gadolinium(III) with some Amino Acids by Potentiometric Method

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WE report herein the results of our investigation on the stability constants of some amino acid complexes with Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} in aqueous solutions having a fixed ionic strength $I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 25° by potentiometric method¹.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Metal and acid contents of metal solutions were determined by acid-base² and complexometric³ methods. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 mol dm^{-3} using 1 mol dm^{-3} (NaClO₄). An Elico LI-10T pH-meter was employed for pH measurements. Potentiometric titrations were carried out at 25° using 0.2 mol dm^{-3} NaOH following the reported procedure^{1,4}. The formation constants (Table 1) have been calculated using method of least-square with the help of a Buzeeby HCL PC/XT computer.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that the formation constant ($\log K_1$) values of Gd^{III} are smaller than those of Sm^{III}. The $\log K_1$ values of Gd^{III} is lower than the earlier